

3 July 2024

Artificial Intelligence Threat Reporting & Incident Response System

Smart cities will be cyber secure with IRIS project!

The project's Pilot Use Cases (PUCs) have been realised successfully! IRIS EU project, held the first round of its three Pilot Use Cases in March 2024 and after having received valuable feedback from the stakeholders who participated, continued with the second and last round in June 2024!

Improving cybersecurity for smart cities is a major advancement that will be made possible by the IRIS project! Completing the project's three Pilot Use Cases in June 2024 was the most important milestone of the project that showcased the capabilities of the IRIS technology solution and evaluated the project's tools.

The 1st Pilot Use Case (PUC 1) held in March 2024 at [CISCO](#) premises in Barcelona, Spain and in June 2024, remotely. PUC 1 was led by the Municipal Institute of Information ([IMI](#)) and its aim was to secure the IoT and control system infrastructure deployed in the tramway station against confidentiality and integrity breaches, promoting safety and security in urban environments and ensuring that trams, pedestrians and bikes can interact safely by mitigating the accidents resulting from man-made cyber-attacks.

The second Pilot Use Case was also held in two rounds in March 2024, remotely and in June 2024, in Tallinn, Estonia. The pilot use case was led by the [Finest Centre for Smart Cities](#) with the aim of protecting the AI-enabled infrastructure of the autonomous transport system (AV shuttle and the Remote Operation Centre) available in Tallinn against potential orchestrated attacks.

[Forum Virium Helsinki](#) led and organized the third Pilot Use Case, which took place online in both rounds. Consortium partners demonstrated the capabilities of Virtual Cyber Range in training CERTs/CSIRTs and validated the capabilities of the IRIS platform in safeguarding the Helsinki Smart Grid environment against cyber threats and vulnerabilities.

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Besides the IRIS consortium partners, several stakeholders from national CERTs, the transportation sector and vulnerable road users, the telecommunication and energy sector and representatives from different municipalities attended the pilots and gave useful feedback regarding not only the technical parts but also about the social acceptance that is an important element of the project.

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Project at a Glance

Acronym	IRIS
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Duration	36 months (September 2021 – August 2024)
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